

An Analytical Study of Anthropology in Research of Vedic Literature.

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ABSTRACT

There is a huge difference between Vedic research and Vedic criticism. Vedic research is the influence of western scholars on India. It is as much a gift as it is a scourge. It cannot be applied to Vedic research because the concepts used in the research methodology are unsuitable. Researchers made two major mistakes in the area of research:

1. They did not focus on Vedic grammar.
2. Used anthropology as a research methodology.

“Anthropology is the science of a group of men and their behavior and production.” contemporary research in Vedic literature Anthropology is very essential and helpful equipment. In western countries, the most cases methodology of the study in Vedic literature is based on anthropological loom only. In this article we can see, what anthropology is. uses in research of Vedic literature and its limitations in research areas of Vedic literature.

Keyword – *Vedic, Culture, Anthropology, Research.*

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Every study differs from the others in terms of its goals and methods. As a result, numerous techniques have been used. The descriptive method will be applied to the current study. And the data used are in this study is based on secondary data.

INTRODUCTION

The word anthropology comprises of two words derived from a Greek “Anthropos” meaning man and “Logos” which means science or systematic study¹.

Anthropology is relatively new subject which came to light in recent century as a part of social sciences. This science of anthropology deals with the extensive study of human societies, culture and their development. To be accurate it is a study of inter group interactions

¹ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/anthropology>

and the works of them. To be precise it is the study of man-kind as a whole. Ancient, present and future are all the subject matters of anthropology.

As Anthropology is a broad subject the researchers in this field started to concentrate on single sub-fields. Because of this there was a creation of different sub-fields or different branches within anthropology namely, (1) Physical anthropology, (2) Archaeology, (3) Social anthropology, (4) Cultural anthropology, (5) Linguistics.²

Fig - 1

These emerged as the major branches of anthropology. Even these major branches comprise many sub-branches within them and even many of the researchers oppose them and

tern natural and cultural anthropology as the standard ones because anthropology makes physical and cultural makeup of man as an important subject topic and all others emerged as the sub-branches of them.

Summing up everything above, anthropology is the study of human birth, development, evolution and life of man kind.

Usage of anthropology in Vedic research

Usage of anthropological perspective in the study of Veda – Upanishads is the recent trend among the researchers these days. Doing so is accompanied by many reason.

1. Anthropology studies the ancient civilizations and cultures for its research on humans. The vedic civilization and culture or vedic era is said to be the oldest.
2. Comparative linguistic studies is one of the major branches of anthropology and Sanskrit is the mother to many of the or as researches claim, most of the languages in the world, it is very essential to study it to enhance the research in linguistic anthropology.
3. Most of the ancient civilizations are now dead only some of their relics are available but the only living ancient civilization and culture is the vedic civilization and culture so the study of vedic civilization, its cultures and works are most important for anthropologists to study human cultural evolution and objective and most lively research of man-kind.

² Edited by M. N. Srinivas - METHOD IN SOCIAL ANTHROPOLOGY - Cambridge University Press, London N.W. 1, England The University of Toronto Press, Toronto 5, Canada – (Introduction Page no - X).

So, because of all the above reasons vedic research became a need in anthropological research.

Vedic research started with the study of comparative linguistics. With the advent of Christian missionaries, administrators and scholars to India there was a inclined interest to study Indian culture and works, to do it there was a need to study Sanskrit. To their surprise there was a striking similarities and many matching words between Sanskrit, Lantin and Greek. As a result of it, anthropologists started a comparative linguistic analysis of European languages with Sanskrit. So, with this lingual comparison the anthropological research entered Vedic research.

After all these anthropologists started a extensive research on one question “who was the creator of Vedic culture?”, in order to solve this a sub-division of physical or natural anthropology called racial anthropology entered into this field. After this the study of vedic culture and civilization became a key part of all the branches of anthropology.

Today anthropology is considered as one of the most important, useful and a ‘must use’ tool in Vedic research. Today, we can claim that every single research on Vedas and Vedic culture in western countries are generally on the basis and on perspective of anthropology.

Anthropology may not be held reliable while understanding Vedic meanings

Anthropology may help in understanding some of the physical concepts of Vedas but when determining the meaning of certain Vedic scripts it may get erroneous. It can’t be taken as a interpreter of Vedas because of certain fundamental an basic errors in anthropology.

Every discipline has its own limitations, so does the discipline of anthropology. Because of these limitations there are certain fundamental errors in anthropology. These errors make anthropological interpretations of certain Vedic excerpts and meanings as invalid and disqualifies its perspective and cannot be held reliable.

Some of the basic fundamental errors in anthropology are as follows

- (1) Anthropology is not a firm discipline –

Importance of any discipline is determined by the firmness of knowledge provided by it. Any discipline to be held reliable or faithful, it should be firm. But the knowledge or information provided by anthropology is not firm. Because anthropology doesn’t have a fixed universally followed firm procedure or structure. So, it’s not a fully settled and established discipline. So, this unstable, loose and distorted field cannot be held as reliable discipline. So, the views and interpretations provided by anthropology may be unreliable.

- (2) Anthropology doesn’t have reliable evidence to prove itself –

Even if anthropology finds or gets a firm structure, the concepts of anthropology may not be held faithful because its very own subject matter is unfaithful.

The concepts of anthropology are based on fossils, relics and historical remains and objects and subjects of pre-historic era. When we are incapable of determining and proving many historic concepts and theories which are readily available to our visible sight, how can we trust the firmness of evidence of prehistoric era?

In the discipline of anthropology, the evidence to prove the objectivity of concepts are minimum and many are based on hypothesis and imagination. So, the concepts of anthropology may prove unfaithful.

For instance, let's consider the classification of human race. These classifications are based on some pieces of bones and skulls. Constructing a whole concept of classification by some pieces of skeletal remains which are found somewhere may turn out to be fanatical and fallacious. Because most of the skeletal remains available to us are from European continent, so classification based on this narrow and fewer evidence may be faulty as there are many places in the world where the excavation has not yet taken place. And continent of Europe is not the origin or birthplace of human kind. So the contemporary classification which are currently believed is not complete as the remains from the next excavations may turn everything upside down. And even many times the found remains may mislead. For instance, take the skull found in Piltdown area on 1911-12 in the region of Sussex, England. This skull made a serious buzz and commotion in scientific field. In the year of 1952, it was declared to be a hoax. Even today this case is famous as Piltdown hoax.

The fact of the matter here is that the evidence which are taken by anthropology to prove its concepts may be based on imaginary evidences or from some unreliable and faulty and inconclusive evidences. So anthropological principles cannot be deemed faithful.³

(3) Cultural and linguistic origins are impossible to determine –

The main goal and objective of anthropology is to find out and reconstruct the original structure and makeup of an language and culture⁴. Which an impossible goal. Because discovering cultural originality of language and culture are highly impossible, because of two important reasons,

- I. Because of natural calamities and through the passage of time language and culture undergoes changes in many aspects or may fully decline.
- II. Its fallacious to believe that even the fossils or remains available or found today is in its original state or structure. Because according to anthropology itself, every culture undergoes changes every instance. This is called as cultural change in anthropology.

So how can we discover the origins of languages and cultures which dates back thousands of centuries? so it is impossible to discover and reconstruct the language or culture in it's original form. To this the following two sets of examples are the best illustrators.

³ A. L. Kroeber - 1948 - Kroeber Anthropology - Oxford & IBH Publishing Shahpur Jat, Delhi. – (Page – 80)

⁴ Nirmal Kumar Bose - 1961 - Cultural Anthropology - Asia Publishing House, Bombay. (Page – 10)

First, the origins of so, called Aryans who according to anthropologists were migrated to India but they couldn't determine from where did they come from.

Second, Sanskrit, Greek, Latin, German and many more languages to which many comparative linguists have framed as the fundamental languages have created the concept of 'Indo European' language to which none of the anthropologists were able to provide or discover its original structure. So even today the concept of Indo-European language is deemed as imaginary and highly theoretical concept.

(4) Anthropology is considered as the study of primitive races or tribes –

Anthropology claims to be the study of complete human race but the observations show that it is reserved in the study of scheduled tribes, wild tribes and uncivilized tribal people. It has till date studied only the tribal peoples who are living in the remote jungles of the world and not much more. So calling anthropology as the study of wild tribes or tribal people may not seem false.

Terming them as wild people or forest people may seem right than calling them tribal people or primitive man. Because the tribal people living today cannot be determined as a original primitive man, who lived in centuries ago inside the jungle. And even anthropology says that primitive man roamed inside the jungle, so terming them as forest people may hold more essence.

In ancient time many of the greatest civilizations and cultures raised and fell. Now people who live in dark alleys and slums of a city are called tribes and primitive man. How we cannot claim that the persons living in slums and dark alleys of the cities as the original residents of the city, in the same way we cannot determine the tribes in jungle as the cultural origins. Even if it was believed, even then the fact that they are uncivilized and they are tribes are undebatable. So now anthropology is reserved for the most part, for the study these tribes. So the concepts of anthropology may find irrelevant and fallacious in the interpretation of vedic culture. Because vedic culture is ancient but is not primitive or uncivilized. The literary works of vedic culture or civilizations like Samhita, Brahmana, Aranyaka, Upanishads etc. cannot be found in any tribal people all over the world. Even modern people are not able to match the literary standards set by it. vedic culture and civilization was a well organized, well oriented and well nourished culture. The study of values and lifestyle of people in vedic culture supports the above statement.

The social life in vedic culture is the revelation of well planned and well reasoned way of leading the life. The aggregate of varna-system shows the planned lifestyle as well as the ashram-system shows a procedural and organizational way of living. This sort of model lifestyle cannot be seen in any of the tribes or societies or civilizations around the world, not even in the modern societies.

Conclusion

In today's scientific world of prosperity and development amidst the ongoing violence, accidents, conflicts, epidemic, global crisis, wars etc., and many middle east countries losing their mental stability and ability due to never ending conflicts and wars, even till

date a culture teaches them peace, non-violence, fraternity and humanity, like for instance by the concepts like ‘Vasudeva Kutumbakam’ and much more, that is Vedic culture. It has given world a medically miraculous lifestyle like yoga and Ayurveda. Terming Vedic culture as wild, unorganised or uncivilized is fallacious, erroneous and foolishness. So viewing Vedic culture as a uncivilized one is stupidity and unscientific.

Summing up everything, while interpreting Vedic meanings usage of anthropological perspective may be erroneous.

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